

Sustainable Financing for Rural Social Enterprises in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of sustainable finance on rural social enterprises in Nigeria, with a focus on rural health services, electricity access, and basic drinking water services. Sustainable funding is critical for small groups' development and sustainability, allowing them to expand their operations and create a greater social impact. Government agencies, financial institutions, and non-profit groups play a vital role in building an enabling climate for these firms. However, institutional constraints, such as restricted access to donor funds, grants, and bonds, impede the development of rural social entrepreneurs. To tackle these issues, a multimodal approach is necessary, including changing the legislative environment, investing in education and skills training, and developing inclusive business practices. The data from 2014 to 2023 from the World Bank reveals that government initiatives expanding access to financing considerably strengthen the operational capacities of rural social entrepreneurs, especially in basic drinking water services. The study proposes promoting distinctive financing methods, such as community-based finance or social impact bonds, to stimulate the development of alternative funding strategies for rural firms.

Keywords: Sustainable Finance, Rural Social Enterprises, Social Impact, Green Bond, Donor Funding, Grants

Introduction

The financial sector wields significant influence in promoting sustainability by funding research into Promoting businesses that adhere to fair and sustainable labor practices is a key focus of this initiative. The concept has emerged as a response to global efforts to address social, racial, and gender disparities. As we navigate this green revolution, we continuously gain insights into sustainability, with new milestones regularly enhancing our understanding.

Sustainable finance involves making investment choices that consider environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors focus on the sustainability and ethical impact of investments activities or projects. Environmental, social, and governance factors are crucial in addressing the climate crisis, ensuring sustainable resources, protecting human and animal rights, and managing of employee relations and compensation in both public and private organizations involves ensuring fair treatment, fostering positive workplace environments, and providing competitive pay and benefits.

The financial sector is essential for combating climate change through aiding the reduction of climate-related risks and lessening the effects of negative climate events. In contrast to green finance, sustainable finance not only limits funding to hard-to-abate industries but also provides financial services to certain brown firms to support their transition to greener practices (Zhang and Zhou, 2023).

Long-term institutional investors can contribute redistribute and balance climate-related hazards, thereby enhancing financial stability. Risk management mechanisms such as Disaster bonds and index insurance provide safeguards against the rising risk of natural disasters, while Green bonds, green stock indices, and voluntary decarbonization are instances of financial instruments initiatives facilitate the reallocation of investments towards environmentally friendly businesses. An unprecedented degree of collaboration across multiple stakeholders has been pushed by the existential risk that climate change presents to both human life and business output (MacDonald et al., 2022).

Cunha et al. (2021) emphasize that achieving the SDGs will necessitate annual investments of approximately \$7 trillion from both public and private sectors. Specifically, addressing climate change requires financial commitments estimated for Low end about around \$2.5 trillion (OECD, 2018), \$3.3 trillion and \$4.5 trillion (UNSDG, 2018) while \$5 trillion and \$7 trillion (UNEP, 2022).

Creditors can play a crucial role in advocating for environmentally friendly legislation during specific periods. They also educate debtors on the significance of sustainable development (Pan et al., 2023; Umar and Safi, 2023). The concept of green credit has become increasingly prominent, expanding its influence as awareness of environmental issues grows.

Researchers, such as Ma et al. (2023), have investigated the effects of green loans on financial institutions. Green loans serve as a bridge between corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives and bank profitability, an aspect that is often overlooked. Allocating financial resources for green projects and assets becomes challenging. Lack of clarity hinders effective risk assessment and mitigation. Unclear definitions impact communication efforts and policy formulation.

Since January 2013, the G20 has actively promoted green credit programs to mitigate environmental harm. Financial institutions can also establish a “green channel” to link eco-friendly companies with investors (Ma et al., 2023).

Statement of the Problem

Climate change poses an immense threat to the entire world, affecting both highly industrialized societies and Rural Social Enterprises. Stakeholders have called for urgent action to prevent irreversible consequences. International treaties, especially the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a set of 17 global objectives designed to address pressing challenges the G20 Sustainable Finance Roadmap (the “Roadmap”), endorsed voluntarily by G20 Leaders at the 2021 Rome Summit and acknowledged by G20 finance ministers and central bank governors, are crucial for achieving the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development is a global framework adopted by all United Nations member states in 2015. These agreements relate with the foundation for international climate negotiations, including the landmark Paris Agreement. Adopted in 2015, the Paris Agreement aims to limit global temperature rise to well below 2°C. Despite scientific evidence, recent reports indicate that progress toward climate targets remains alarmingly slow (IPCC, 2023; UNEP, 2022).

The G20 Sustainable Finance Working Group (SFWG) was entrusted by Finance Ministers and Central Bank Governors to produce a G20 Sustainable Finance Roadmap, directing the attention of the G20, international organizations, and stakeholders towards the core objectives of the sustainable finance agenda.

International organizations are working to grasp the problems and rewards of sustainability reporting for SMEs and emerging market economies, in line with G20 Sustainable Finance Working Group Action 09, by utilizing digital technologies, enhancing capacity-building initiatives, and enhancing information efficiency.

Social enterprises in Nigeria, particularly those operating in rural areas, encounter significant barriers in obtaining financing. these challenges are worsened via combinations due to various factors, such as restricted access to traditional financing, rigorous grant application processes, economic and political instability, lack of awareness and support and inadequate government support.

In summary, the sustainability of rural social enterprises in Nigeria is jeopardized by limited access to financing, rigorous application processes, economic instability, lack of awareness, and insufficient government support. Addressing these issues is crucial for enhancing the capacity of these enterprises to deliver social value and contribute to rural development effectively.

Conceptual framework

Fig. 1: showing the relationship between sustainable finance and social rural enterprises in Nigeria.

Source: Researcher, (2024).

Gap in literature

Understanding the research trends in green finance within rural economic areas offers valuable insights into sustainable finance practices. By analyzing scholarly contributions, this study seeks to investigate the barriers, possibilities, and best practices linked with applying sustainable financial principles. Such insights may develop particular policies and activities that align with each country's socio-economic realities and environmental concerns (Kumari and Jaiswal, 2023).

The pursuit of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) necessitates a comprehensive mobilization of societal resources towards achieving sustainability (UNEP, 2022; UNFCCC, 2016). This study posits that countries with high performance, especially those in the European Union (EU), are anticipated to exhibit a greater public interest in sustainable finance. While recent research has highlighted the effect of sustainable finance and investments on SDG outcomes (Ziolo et al., 2020), there is a scarcity of studies exploring how SDG performance influences sustainable finance.

To address this gap, we employ a two-level fixed effects methodology to analyze the effects of both sociodemographic and contextual factors. Our analysis is based on a Eurobarometer survey conducted across all 27 EU nations included a representative sample of 27,862 individuals. We build upon previous research examining public attitudes towards sustainable practices, focusing on individual-level influences as well as broader contextual or the broad-scale effects (de Boer & Aiking, 2023; Long et al., 2023; Sun et al., 2019). The existing studies often generalize financing challenges across various sectors without delving into the unique needs and contexts of rural social enterprises. More targeted research is needed to identify sector-specific financing strategies that address the distinct challenges faced by these enterprises in rural areas.

Addressing these gaps in literature is essential for developing a robust understanding of sustainable financing for rural social enterprises in Nigeria. Future research should focus on innovative financing models, the influence of policy frameworks, sector-specific strategies, financial literacy, and longitudinal assessments to create a comprehensive

framework that supports the sustainability of these enterprises in addressing social challenges.

Research Objectives

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between sustainable financing and social rural enterprises in Nigeria. The study seeks to:

1. evaluate the relationship between sustainable finance and explanatory variables.
2. investigate the relationship between the sustainable finance and Rural Basic Drinking Water Services in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study of sustainable financing and rural social enterprises in Nigeria, focusing on the rural population growth and other economic indicators. Specifically, the research tries to address the following questions:

1. How do financial strategies impact the sustainability of rural social enterprises in Nigeria?
2. What role does government policy play in facilitating access to financing for rural social enterprises?

Hypotheses

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the sources of financing and explanatory variables (Rural Population growth and Access to Electricity).

H₂: Government policies that promote access to financing significantly enhance the operational capacity of rural social enterprises.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Sustainable Financing (predictor variable)

Sustainable financing is increasingly recognized as a critical factor in assessing the financial health and future viability of organizations, particularly in the paradigm of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria. Various studies have explored the predictors of financial sustainability, highlighting the importance of specific financial metrics and operational efficiencies. In summary, the predictors of financial sustainability encompass a range of financial and operational metrics, including profitability, cash flow,

risk management, and sustainable investment practices. Understanding these variables can help organizations strategize effectively to enhance their long-term viability and attract sustainable financing.

Bonds

Sustainable bonds or loans refer to bond issuances where the issuer pledges to utilize the proceeds for financing environmental or social initiatives. These sustainable bonds share the same financial and contractual characteristics as any other senior unsecured transaction, such as conventional bonds. However, when issuing a sustainable bond, the issuer commits to designate the proceeds specifically for environmental and/or social projects or expenditures, based on a predetermined set of eligibility criteria and ultimately supply investors with reports detailing the projects funded by the proceeds from the sustainable bond.

Donor Funding

Donor funding remains critical for sustainable financing in Nigeria, innovative approaches that emphasize domestic resource mobilization, public-private partnerships, and collaborative efforts are essential to address the challenges posed by declining international aid. Multilateral organizations like the United Nations, World Bank, and Commonwealth Secretariat, along with regional entities such as the European Union, African Union, and SADC, have provided funding to NGOs, initiatives, and programs. These subsidies are distributed via non-governmental organizations aim to promote development and enhance service delivery in rural areas.

Grants

Grants are monetary contributions provided by governments, organizations, or foundations to fund particular projects or initiatives. These funds do not require repayment, making them an appealing option for various purposes. Nigeria's commitment to sustainable financing reflects a broader strategy to achieve economic growth while addressing pressing environmental and social issues. The collaborative efforts between government, financial institutions, and international partners are essential for the success of these initiatives. Organizations like Oracle are also contributing through environmental grants aimed at supporting biodiversity and sustainable development initiatives in Nigeria. These grants help local enterprises and NGOs implement projects that address environmental challenges and promote sustainability. The African Development Bank (AfDB) launched a three-year

maturity Social Bond worth \$3 billion, titled “Fight Covid-19,” which carries a coupon rate of 0.75 percent. The funds raised through this bond are intended to support healthcare services, infrastructure, and economic relief efforts for the African population.

Rural Social Enterprises (criterion variable)

Rural social enterprises (RSEs) are organizations that operate in rural areas and aim to create positive social change through entrepreneurial, market-based approaches. They reinvest their profits back into the community to create positive social change.

Rural social enterprises are an innovative approach to rural development that harnesses entrepreneurial strategies to create positive social impact. While facing unique challenges, RSEs have significant potential to address rural issues and drive community-led change.

Current Health Services

Studies indicate that while rural social enterprises can play a crucial role in enhancing health outcomes and providing essential services, their sustainability is often jeopardized by inadequate funding and a lack of formal training for those managing these enterprises. This situation is exacerbated by the economic constraints and demographic challenges in rural areas. While rural social enterprises have the potential to significantly impact health outcomes, their effectiveness is contingent upon adequate funding, capacity building, and supportive policies that address the unique challenges of rural health care delivery.

Access to Electricity

Access to electricity has a more pronounced effect on small home businesses compared to larger enterprises. For example, the availability of electric refrigeration has allowed home-based businesses to thrive, enabling them to offer services like food preservation and cold storage. Studies indicate that access to electricity boosts household incomes and enhances entrepreneurial activities in rural areas. For instance, rural electrification programs have been shown to lead to the establishment of small-scale industries, which utilize local resources and labor, thereby creating jobs and fostering economic growth.

Access to Rural Basic Drinking Water Services

In rural areas, this pressing issue is being increasingly tackled by social enterprises through innovative and sustainable models. Access to rural water services remains a challenge, social enterprises can play a role in improving the situation by developing innovative,

affordable, and sustainable water supply solutions tailored to rural communities. Partnering with the government and development organizations to implement water projects in underserved areas. Engage with local communities to ensure water services are accessible, reliable, and maintained. Explore opportunities for public-private partnerships and impact investment to scale up rural water initiatives.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation for examining the relationship between sustainable financing for rural social enterprises in Nigeria in this study is grounded in two key theories which are social capital theory and stakeholder theory.

Social Capital Theory

Social capital theory (SCT), as articulated by Bourdieu (1985) refers to the aggregate of the actual or potential resources linked to the possession of a durable network of institutionalized relationships of mutual acquaintance or recognition. The key idea is that a network gives value to its members by enabling them access to the social resources inherent within it (Bourdieu, 1985; Florin, Lubatkin, & Schulze, 2003). This theory is a multifaceted concept that explores the value and advantages gained from social networks and relationships. It suggests that social networks can be viewed as a form of capital, akin to physical or human capital, which can be utilized for social and economic benefits.

Social capital is built through networks of relationships among individuals and organizations. These networks may enable access to information, resources, and opportunities that may not be accessible otherwise. Trust within a community enhances cooperation and collective action. When individuals trust each other, they are more likely to share resources and support each other's initiatives. Shared norms and values within a community can facilitate collaboration and mutual support. These norms often include expectations of reciprocity and collective responsibility.

Relevance to the study

Social networks can enhance access to financial resources, information, and markets that might be otherwise inaccessible. Strong social capital can help rural social enterprises withstand economic shocks and challenges by providing a support network. Trust and shared values facilitate collaboration among community members, leading to more effective and sustainable development initiatives.

Stakeholder theory

This concept pertains to a framework for business ethics and organizational management as described by Schaltegger et al. (2019). Stakeholder Theory asserts that companies attempt to provide multiple benefits for different stakeholders, including organizations and individuals who may affect or be influenced by the company, such as civil societies, communities, customers, workers, governments, shareholders, and suppliers (Freeman, 1984).

Donaldson and Preston (1995) built upon Freeman's ideas by asserting that companies have a moral responsibility to consider the interests of all stakeholders. They argued that effective stakeholder management can enhance long-term profitability. They identified three theoretical frameworks for engaging with stakeholders involves understanding and addressing their concerns, interests, and expectations through the followings:

Descriptive Approach: This approach analyses organizations as formed of many stakeholder groups, each having distinct interests. It is the least comprehensive technique, creating the basis for examining stakeholder claims or concerns.

Instrumental Approach: This viewpoint highlights the importance of stakeholder management owing of its excellent effect on financial achievement. It represents a more advanced perspective that seeks to balance financial and stakeholder interests.

Normative Approach: This framework places stakeholders as the ultimate goal rather than merely a means to achieve financial success. It is the most thorough perspective, concentrating exclusively on the stakeholders themselves.

Relevance to the study

Rural social enterprises can engage with local communities to understand their needs and incorporate their feedback into business decisions. This can enhance trust and cooperation for Community engagement. By considering the environmental impact of their operations, rural social enterprises can adopt more sustainable practices that benefit both the community and the environment. Ensuring fair wages, good working conditions, and opportunities for growth can improve employee satisfaction and productivity.

Empirical Review:

The literature review will explore existing studies on sustainable financing for rural social enterprises and their intersections. It will critically analyze theoretical perspectives, empirical findings, and case studies from Nigeria and comparable economies to provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter.

Akanfe, et al. (2019) study explores the role of The study investigates the role of rural finance in poverty reduction in Nigeria, focused on micro and small companies in Ogun State, where financial sector reforms have been implemented since the 1980s. Despite these reforms, financial services have not been developed for the rural population, which numbers 70-80% of the general population and 90% of the destitute. The research uses a survey research design and the OLS regression method to analyze the impact of rural financing on poverty reduction. The results show a favorable relationship between rural finance and poverty reduction in Nigeria, suggesting that measures should be implemented to encourage rural financing. The study highlights the need for continued efforts to address poverty in rural areas.

Zabolotnyy and Wasilewski (2019) completed a study assessing the financial sustainability of 12 food firms in Northern Europe over a period from 2005 to 2015. They defined financial sustainability by measures such as net profit/equity, total assets/current assets, price/book value, and revenue/total assets. Using fuzzy set logic, they developed aggregated assessments of value, continuity, and financial sustainability. Their study focused on understanding how these financial indicators contribute to the overall sustainability of the companies, but it did not analyse the relationship with an outcome variable, unlike other studies that might investigate direct repercussions on certain outcomes. The study does not investigate a relationship with an outcome variable, unlike Gómez-Bezares et al. (2017).

Henock's (2019) study investigates the financial sustainability and profitability of 33 Savings and Credit Cooperative Societies (SACCOs) in Eastern Ethiopia over the period from 2017 to 2019. The investigation showed that while these SACCOs are economically viable, they are not financially viable. This shows that although they gain profits, corporations encounter difficulties in sustaining long-term financial health. The study underscores the importance of social effect in business and investment decision-making, emphasising the necessity for sustainable firm models that bring benefits to the economy, society, and the environment.

Adegoke et al. (2022) conducted a study on Nigeria's financial challenges and sustainable government financial support for SMEs. They analyzed data from 700 SMEs in Southwest Nigeria, identifying issues like poor program design, favoritism in disbursement, low awareness, and difficult access procedures. The study recommends a result-based

financing framework, including a guarantee scheme for loans without collateral and lower interest rates.

Ogunjimi and Adebayo (2019) the research evaluated the link between health expenditure, health outcomes, and economic development in Nigeria from 1981 to 2017. It employed the Toda-Yamamoto causality model and the Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test to study these relationships. The findings demonstrated a unidirectional correlation between health spending and infant mortality, life expectancy and maternal mortality, and real GDP to health expenditure. The report proposes that the Nigerian government raise health spending to fulfil the WHO's guideline of dedicating at least 13% of its yearly budget to the health sector for effective financing. Modern technology and professional health staff services should be sought to counteract the high prevalence of mother and newborn mortality in the health sector. The research also revealed no connection between real GDP and infant mortality.

Methodology

This research employs a quantitative methodology with a descriptive approach grounded in positivist philosophy, focusing on specific populations or samples. Data collection is carried out using research instruments, followed by quantitative or statistical analysis, aimed at testing established hypotheses. The descriptive approach determines the presence of an independent variable, either by examining one or more independent variables or by comparing variables to explore their interrelationships.

Model specification

We can use these variables to build a regression model with the relationship between these variables can be expressed in a linear regression model as follows:

$$SF = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BND + \beta_2 DNR + \beta_3 GRT + \beta_4 CHE + \beta_5 ATE + \beta_6 BDW + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$SF = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BND + \beta_2 DNR + \beta_3 GRT + \beta_4 CHE + \beta_5 ATE + \beta_6 BDW + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where:

SFSF = Sustainable Financing

β_0 = Intercept

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$ = Coefficients for each independent variable

ϵ = Error term

The model can be estimated using techniques like Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Robust Standard Errors, or Panel Data Analysis, depending on the data structure.

$$LOGSF = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BND + \beta_2 DNR + \beta_3 GRT + \beta_4 CHE + \beta_5 ATE + \beta_6 BDW + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

where α represents the intercept. LOG represents the natural logarithm. α represent the intercept while ϵ represent the error term.

Table 1: Description of symbols and measurements instruments

Symbol	Description	Source	Measurement
BND	Portfolio investment, bonds	World Development Indicator (2023)	(PPG + PNG) (NFL, Current US\$)
DNR	Net official flows from UN agencies	World Development Indicator (2023)	(current US\$)
GRT	Grants, excluding technical cooperation	World Development Indicator (2023)	(BoP, current S\$)
CHE	Current Health Expenditure	World Development Indicator (2023)	(Current Int'l \$)
ATE	Rural Access to rural Electricity	World Development Indicator (2023)	(% of rural population)
BDW	People using at least basic drinking water services	World Development Indicator (2023)	(% of rural population)

Hypotheses:

H₀: Effective financial strategies positively influence the long-term performance of rural social enterprises.

Table 2:

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	CHE	132.281 ^a	1	132.281	.300	.604
	ATE	4.561 ^b	1	4.561	.306	.600
	BDW	.004 ^c	1	.004	.000	.988
Intercept	CHE	103500.033	1	103500.033	234.610	.000
	ATE	2558.928	1	2558.928	171.751	.000
	BDW	10415.522	1	10415.522	639.895	.000
BND	CHE	132.281	1	132.281	.300	.604
	ATE	4.561	1	4.561	.306	.600
	BDW	.004	1	.004	.000	.988

a. R Squared = .048 (Adjusted R Squared = -.111)

b. R Squared = .049 (Adjusted R Squared = -.110)

c. R Squared = .000 (Adjusted R Squared = -.167)

The corrected model analysis results indicate that none of the financial strategies significantly influence the performance metrics (CHE, ATE, and BDW) at conventional levels ($p < .05$). The F-values are low, and the significance values are all above .05, suggesting that there is no statistically significant effect of the financial strategies on these performance measures. In contrast, the intercept model analysis shows highly significant results for all dependent variables with p-values of 0.000. This suggests that while the overall model is significant, it does not imply that the specific financial strategies tested in the corrected model have a positive influence on performance. Based on the provided data, the hypothesis (H_0) that effective financial strategies positively influence long-term performance is not supported by the corrected model results. The intercept model indicates that there may be underlying factors contributing to performance, but these factors are not captured by the financial strategies assessed in this analysis. **H₁**: The incorporation of social innovation in financing approaches leads to improved outcomes for rural social enterprises compared to traditional financing methods.

Table 3:

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	CHE	79.261 ^a	1	79.261	.176	.689
	ATE	20.877 ^b	1	20.877	1.714	.238
	BDW	33.575 ^c	1	33.575	3.143	.127
Intercept	CHE	12930.664	1	12930.664	28.735	.002
	ATE	122.547	1	122.547	10.062	.019
	BDW	1449.573	1	1449.573	135.705	.000
DNR	CHE	79.261	1	79.261	.176	.689
	ATE	20.877	1	20.877	1.714	.238
	BDW	33.575	1	33.575	3.143	.127

a. R Squared = .029 (Adjusted R Squared = -.133)

b. R Squared = .209 (Adjusted R Squared = .178)

c. R Squared = .344 (Adjusted R Squared = .234)

The significance levels indicate that none of the dependent variables showed statistically significant results at the conventional alpha level of 0.05, as all p-values exceed this threshold. CHE ($p = 0.689$), ATE ($p = 0.238$), and BDW ($p = 0.127$) indicate that the differences observed are not statistically significant. The R-squared values suggest varying levels of explained variance in the dependent variables: CHE explains only about 2.9% of the variance. ATE explains 22.2%, indicating a moderate relationship. BDW explains 34.4%, suggesting a stronger relationship compared to the others. The adjusted R-squared values provide insight into how well the model fits the data while accounting for the number of predictors: CHE has a negative adjusted R-squared, indicating a poor model fit. ATE and BDW show slight positive adjusted values, suggesting some explanatory power.

The analysis indicates that incorporating social innovation in financing approaches does not lead to significantly improved outcomes for rural social enterprises when compared to traditional financing methods based on the metrics provided. The lack of statistical significance across all dependent variables implies that further investigation may be necessary to explore other factors or methodologies that could yield more conclusive results regarding the effectiveness of social innovation in financing rural enterprises.

H₀₂: Government policies that promote access to financing significantly enhance the operational capacity of rural social enterprises.

Table 4:

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	CHE	22.663 ^a	1	22.663	.049	.832
	ATE	8.159 ^b	1	8.159	.571	.479
	BDW	73.332 ^c	1	73.332	18.081	.005
Intercept	CHE	11624.073	1	11624.073	25.301	.002
	ATE	377.852	1	377.852	26.425	.002
	BDW	694.005	1	694.005	171.119	.000
GRT	CHE	22.663	1	22.663	.049	.832
	ATE	8.159	1	8.159	.571	.479
	BDW	73.332	1	73.332	18.081	.005

a. R Squared = .008 (Adjusted R Squared = -.157)

b. R Squared = .087 (Adjusted R Squared = -.065)

c. R Squared = .751 (Adjusted R Squared = .709)

The data presents several dependent variables (CHE, ATE, BDW) with their corresponding Type III Sum of Squares, degrees of freedom (df), Mean Square, F-statistic, and significance levels (Sig.). The findings revealed that CHE: $F(1,1) = 0.049$, Sig. = 0.832, R Squared = 0.008 (Adjusted R Squared = -0.157), ATE: $F(1,1) = 0.571$, Sig. = 0.479, R Squared = 0.087 (Adjusted R Squared = -0.065), BDW: $F(1,1) = 18.081$, Sig. = 0.005, R Squared = 0.751 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.709). From this analysis, it is evident that while CHE and ATE show no significant relationship with the independent variables (high p-values), BDW demonstrates a significant effect with a low p-value (0.005). The high R Squared value for BDW indicates that a substantial portion of the variance in this dependent variable is explained by the model. The statistical analysis indicates that while some dependent variables do not show significant relationships with financing policies, the strong significance found in BDW suggests that certain aspects of government financing policies do enhance operational capacities of rural

social enterprises. Moreover, supporting literature reinforces the idea that targeted financial interventions and innovative financing models can significantly improve the performance and sustainability of these enterprises. Thus, Ho3 is supported by both statistical evidence and empirical research findings indicating that government policies promoting access to financing are crucial for enhancing the operational capacity of rural social enterprises.

However, several studies support the notion that access to financing enhances the operational capacity of rural social enterprises such as Fiamohe, et al.,(2021), access to financing for Productive Employment Opportunities for Women in Rural Benin for Partnership for Economic Policy Working Paper Series found that social-network-based financing significantly improves business performance for rural women entrepreneurs compared to traditional financing methods and Borges, et al., (2015) study found that entrepreneurship institutions play a crucial role in improving access to micro-financing for rural enterprises, which in turn supports sustainability and productivity. This aligns with the idea that government policies facilitating such institutions can bolster operational capacity.

Table 5: Correlations

		BND	DNR	GRT	CHE	ATE	BDW
BND	Pearson Correlation	1	.388	.283	.218	-.204	-.185
DNR	Pearson Correlation	.388	1	-.355	-.169	.463	-.595
GRT	Pearson Correlation	.283	-.355	1	.090	-.288	.840**
CHE	Pearson Correlation	.218	-.169	.090	1	-.129	.096
ATE	Pearson Correlation	-.204	.463	-.288	-.129	1	-.202
BDW	Pearson Correlation	-.185	-.595	.840**	.096	-.202	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlation analysis shows that BND correlates positively with DNR (0.388). DNR Shows a strong negative correlation with BDW (-0.595) which correlates negatively with GRT (-0.355) and positively with ATE (0.463). GRT exhibits a strong positive correlation with BDW (0.840), indicating that as GRT increases, BDW tends to increase as well. Shows a negative correlation with DNR (-0.355). CHE has no significant correlations with other variables. ATE displays a positive correlation with DNR (0.463) and a negative correlation with GRT (-0.288). BDW indicates strongly correlates positively with GRT (0.840) and negatively with DNR (-0.595).

Significant correlations show that only correlations that are statistically significant at the 0.01 level are GRT and BDW: $r=0.840$ ($r=0.840$ (significant) which indicates a strong

positive relationship, suggesting that higher values of GRT are associated with higher values of BDW. DNR and BDW: $r=-0.595$ (significant). This shows a moderate negative relationship, implying that as DNR increases, BDW tends to decrease. Non-significant correlations do not meet the significance threshold of 0.01: BND and DNR (0.388), DNR and GRT (-0.355), ATE and DNR (0.463). CHE does not show any significant relationships.

Findings

Based on the significant findings related to BDW in both the statistical analysis and correlation matrix, there is sufficient evidence to accept the hypothesis that government policies promoting access to financing do significantly enhance the operational capacity of rural social enterprises, particularly as measured by BDW. However, it is also important to consider the mixed results for CHE and ATE, which indicate that while some aspects of operational capacity are positively affected by financing policies, others may not be as influenced. This suggests a nuanced understanding of how different dimensions of operational capacity respond to such policies.

Final Decision

Accept the overall result regarding the positive impact of government financing policies on enhancing the operational capacity of rural social enterprises, specifically through measures like BDW. Further exploration may be warranted to understand the varying impacts on other measures like CHE and ATE.

Implications of Results

The findings collectively indicate that addressing these hypothesis policies aimed at enhancing access to financing play a crucial role in improving certain aspects of operational capacity within rural social enterprises. Specifically:

Effective Financing Leads to Growth: The significant relationship between GRT and BDW suggests that targeted financial support can facilitate growth in rural enterprises, which is essential for their sustainability and success.

Need for Comprehensive Support: The lack of significant results for CHE and ATE implies that enhancing operational capacity may require a multifaceted approach beyond just financial support. It is essential to consider additional factors such as training, resource access, and community engagement.

Strategic Policy Development: Policymakers should focus on creating comprehensive strategies that not only provide funding but also foster an environment conducive to growth through training, mentorship, and collaboration among stakeholders.

Summary

Correlation Coefficients states that the Pearson Correlation values range from -1 to 1. Values closer to 1 imply a strong positive correlation, values closer to -1 imply a strong negative correlation, and values closer to 0 imply no or very weak linear relationship. Significance Levels of (2-tailed) values indicate whether the correlations are statistically significant. A common threshold for significance is 0.05. Values below this threshold suggest that the correlation is statistically significant. Conclusive findings show that BND and DNR correlation is 0.388 with a Sig. value of 0.303, indicating a moderate positive correlation but not statistically significant. BDW and GRT correlation is -0.595 with a Sig. value of 0.091, indicating a moderate negative correlation but not statistically significant. CHE and ATE correlation is -0.129 with a Sig. value of 0.822, indicating a very weak negative correlation and not statistically significant.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made to address the enhancement of rural social enterprises

Develop Tailored Financial Products: Create financing options specifically designed for rural social enterprises, considering their unique challenges and needs. This could include low-interest loans, grants, or micro-financing initiatives.

Promote Innovative Financing Models: Encourage the use of alternative financing models such as community-based funding, crowdfunding, or social impact bonds that can provide flexible capital to rural enterprises.

Training and Development: Implement training programs focused on financial literacy, business management, and operational efficiency for rural entrepreneurs. This will empower them to utilize financing effectively.

Mentorship Programs: Establish mentorship networks connecting experienced entrepreneurs with emerging rural social enterprises to share best practices and strategies for growth.

Foster Collaboration: Encourage partnerships between government agencies, NGOs, and private sector stakeholders to create a supportive ecosystem for rural social enterprises.

Enhance Access to Resources: Improve access to information about available funding opportunities and resources through centralized platforms or local community centers.

Advocate for Policy Reforms: Work towards policy changes that reduce bureaucratic barriers for rural social enterprises seeking funding. Simplifying application processes can increase participation in financing programs.

Monitor and Evaluate Policies: Establish mechanisms for ongoing evaluation of government policies related to financing rural enterprises to ensure they are meeting intended goals and making necessary adjustments based on feedback.

Encourage Sustainable Practices: Promote environmentally friendly practices within rural social enterprises that can attract additional funding sources focused on sustainability.

Diversify Revenue Streams: Support initiatives that help rural enterprises diversify their income sources to reduce dependency on a single funding source.

Utilize Digital Platforms: Encourage the use of digital tools and platforms for marketing, sales, and financial management to enhance operational efficiency and broaden market reach.

Access to Online Training Resources: Provide access to online courses and resources that can help rural entrepreneurs build skills relevant to modern business practices.

Relevance of the Study

The study highlights the importance of social enterprises in contributing to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It suggests that by focusing on social impact, these enterprises can achieve economic and social objectives, especially in rural communities. The study emphasizes the need for sustainable financing to empower rural social enterprises in Nigeria. It calls for government, financial institutions, and other stakeholders to create an environment that supports the growth of social enterprises, leading to sustainable rural development and improved quality of life.

References

- Adegoke, J. F., Nwankpa, N. N., Bakare, L. A., Tijani, S. A., & Zubair, O. J. (2022). Financial Gap and Sustainable Government Financial Interventions to Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Nigeria: Developing a Sustainable Framework. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 10(1), 25–43. <https://doi.org/10.37745/ijbmr.vol10no1p25-43>
- Auh, S., & Menguc, B. (2005). Top management team diversity and innovativeness: The moderating role of interfunctional coordination. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 34(3), 249–261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2004.09.005>
- de Boer, J., & Aiking, H. (2017). Pursuing a Low Meat Diet to Improve Both Health and Sustainability: How Can We Use the Frames that Shape Our Meals? *Ecological Economics*, 142(142), 238–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.06.037>
- de Camargo Fiorini, P., Roman Pais Seles, B. M., Chiappetta Jabbour, C. J., Barberio Mariano, E., & de Sousa Jabbour, A. B. L. (2018). Management theory and big data literature: From a review to a research agenda. *International Journal of Information Management*, 43(43), 112–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2018.07.005>
- Donaldson, T., & Preston, L. E. (1995). The Stakeholder Theory of the Corporation: Concepts, Evidence, and Implications. *The Academy of Management Review*, 20(1), 65–91. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258887>
- Freeman, R. E. (1984). Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach. In *research.monash.edu*. Cambridge University Press. <https://research.monash.edu/en/publications/strategic-management-a-stakeholder-approach>
- Gonul Ogotveren , O., & Senyuva, Z. (2020). How Social Entrepreneurs Can Create Impact for a Better World. *Entrepreneur and Innovation Exchange*, 34(8-97). <https://doi.org/10.32617/459-5e69faa31fceb>
- IPCC. (2019). *2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories — IPCC*. [ipcc.ch; IPCC. https://www.ipcc.ch/report/2019-refinement-to-the-2006-ipcc-guidelines-for-national-greenhouse-gas-inventories/](https://www.ipcc.ch/report/2019-refinement-to-the-2006-ipcc-guidelines-for-national-greenhouse-gas-inventories/)

- IPCC. (2022). *Climate change: a Threat to Human Wellbeing and Health of the planet. Taking Action Now Can Secure Our Future — IPCC*. IPCC.
<https://www.ipcc.ch/2022/02/28/pr-wgii-ar6/>
- Kumlachew, M. (2020). Effect of Outreach on Financial Sustainability and Profitability of Saving and Credit Cooperatives in Eastern Ethiopia. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 11(15). <https://doi.org/10.7176/rjfa/11-15-02>
- Ma, M., Zhu, X., Liu, M., & Huang, X. (2023). Combining the role of green finance and environmental sustainability on green economic growth: Evidence from G-20 economies. *Renewable Energy*, 207(207), 128–136.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.02.046>
- Mondejar, M. E., Avtar, R., Diaz, H. L. B., Dubey, R. K., Esteban, J., Gómez-Morales, A., Hallam, B., Mbungu, N. T., Okolo, C. C., Prasad, K. A., She, Q., & Garcia-Segura, S. (2021). Digitalization to Achieve Sustainable Development goals: Steps Towards a Smart Green Planet. *Science of the Total Environment*, 794(148539), 148539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.148539>
- Ogunjimi, J. A., & Adebayo, A. O. (2019). Health Expenditure, Health Outcomes and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics and Empirical Research*, 6(2), 130–139. <https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.501.2019.62.130.139>
- Olumekor, M., & Oke, A. (2024). Support for sustainable finance and investment in Europe. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 449(141769), 141769–141769.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.141769>
- Pan, W., Cao, H., & Liu, Y. (2023). “Green” innovation, privacy regulation and environmental policy. *Renewable Energy*, 203(104), 245–254.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.12.025>
- Safi, A., Wei, X., Sansaloni, E. M., & Umar, M. (2023). Breaking down the complexity of sustainable development: A focus on resources, economic complexity, and innovation. *Resources Policy*, 83(103), 103746.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2023.103746>
- Semaw Henock, M. (2019). Financial sustainability and outreach performance of saving and credit cooperatives: The case of Eastern Ethiopia. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 24(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmrv.2018.08.001>

- Sun, H., Pofoura, A. K., Adjei Mensah, I., Li, L., & Mohsin, M. (2020). The role of environmental entrepreneurship for sustainable development: Evidence from 35 countries in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Science of the Total Environment*, 741(3), 140132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.140132>
- Sun, X., Zhou, C., & Gan, Z. (2023). Green Finance Policy and ESG Performance: Evidence from Chinese Manufacturing Firms. *Sustainability*, 15(8), 6781. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15086781>
- Sustainable Finance Working Group, G. (2021). *G20 Sustainable Finance Roadmap*. <https://g20sfwg.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/G20-Sustainable-Finance-Roadmap.pdf>
- Williams, M. (2023). A Digital Business Innovation and Financial Inclusion: Panacea to Nigeria's Economic Growth. *International Journal of Innovation and Business Strategy (IJIBS)*, 18(2), 49–62. <https://doi.org/10.11113/ijibs.v18.142>
- Xia, L., Fatema, N., Rahman, M., & Rahman, Md. M. (2024). Does Green Financing Moderate the Effect of Trade Openness on Carbon Emissions in Emerging Countries? *Sage Open*, 14(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241285179>
- Yimka Samson Akanfe, A., Olusegun, A., Idowu Aderonke, N., & Modupe, O. (2019). Rural Financing as a Panacea for Poverty Alleviation: A Study of Selected Micro and Small Enterprises in Ogun State. *Journal of Business and Economic Development*, 4(3), 81. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jbed.20190403.12>
- Yitayaw, M. K. (2021). Determinants of Profitability and Financial Sustainability of Saving and Credit Cooperatives in Eastern Ethiopia. *International Journal of Rural Management*, 17(2), 097300522098059. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0973005220980599>
- Zabolotnyy, S., & Wasilewski, M. (2019). The Concept of Financial Sustainability Measurement: A Case of Food Companies from Northern Europe. *Sustainability*, 11(18), 5139. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11185139>